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THE EVERYDAY LIFE OF UKRAINIANS IN THE UKRAINIAN SSR AND POLAND IN THE 1920S

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Abstract

The article examines everyday life in Ukrainian society in Soviet Ukraine and Poland in the 1920s. Ukraine lost its independence as a result of four Russian military aggressions, accompanied by lies, manipulation, propaganda (there are no Russian troops in Ukraine, it is a civil war, etc.) and the creation of a puppet government. Poland, on the other hand, with the help of the Entente, managed to preserve its statehood, which included the western Ukrainian lands. Although Russia waged an aggressive war there, created a puppet government, proclaimed a socialist Soviet republic, and after the signing of the peace treaty tried to overthrow the Polish government. So, experience also shows that Russia does not adhere to any signed peace treaty, but perceives it as preparation for another attack. The lives of Ukrainians in Poland and Soviet Ukraine were very different. The Bolshevik Russian occupation authorities imposed a totalitarian form of government. Ukrainians suffered from Russification, terror, repression, the artificially created famine of 1921-1923, and later the genocide of 1932-1933. Fear and defencelessness before the authorities reigned in the country. The Bolsheviks physically exterminated all dissidents and instilled hatred towards them. People had to work hard, live in barracks, and make do with minimal living conditions and other conditions that were barely sufficient for physical survival. The population of the western Ukrainian lands of the Polish state also suffered from various political restrictions and a low standard of living. The policy of forced assimilation, the elimination of Ukrainian schools, the ban on the Ukrainian language in state institutions, police political pressure, the transformation of Ukrainian territory into a raw material appendage and, finally, the creation of a concentration camp had a negative impact on the lives of Ukrainians. However, they were not restricted in their right to move freely, there was no nationalization of property or mass looting, no monopolization of power with the violent imposition of the Bolshevik worldview, and no complete physical destruction of certain social groups. Therefore, Ukrainians in Poland had slightly more freedom and a better standard of living compared to Soviet reality, but it was worse than that of Poles or the populations of neighboring European countries.

Keywords: Ukraine, Poland, Russian occupation, population, everyday life, terror, repression, famine, assimilation, prohibitions.

Introduction

Ukraine and Poland are linked by long-standing historical ties and share a common experience of relations in such states as the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, the Russian Empire and the Austro-Hungarian Empire. Both countries experienced aggression from Bolshevik Russia, which concealed its attack by openly lying and creating puppet governments there. In Ukraine, this was the Provisional Workers' and Peasants' Government headed by Pyatakov in Kursk (Russia) on 28 November 1918, which was later restored in Kharkiv, and in Poland, it was the Workers' and Peasants' Government headed by F. Dzerzhinsky. In July 1920, the Galician Socialist Soviet Republic was even proclaimed. However, Poland managed to defend its independence. A more sad fate awaited Ukraine, which was unable to break free from the 'Bolshevik-Russian embrace.' Both countries have experience of Russian occupation, the struggle for independence and their own national heroes, and neither side has the right to dictate to the other whom to honor [22].

Literature Review

Research into the everyday life of Ukrainians in the 1920s can be divided into several parts. The first part includes studies that examined Soviet reality, in which a new historical community – the Soviet people – was created on the basis of Leninist-Stalinist policies. Demographic losses and ethno-national changes in the population [1; 4], social structure [7], urbanization processes [15], as well as everyday aspects of life, social protection [12], gender aspects of the Soviet sociocultural space [5], deviant behavior [13; 17], etc. This concerned the process of lumpenisation of the population, when the leadership of the USSR pursued a policy against the people, especially against Ukrainians, through terror, repression, and the organization of famine with the aim of eliminating any opposition, rapid industrialization for the militarization of the country and the consolidation of industrial units, and most importantly, the formation of a new consciousness and the absolute dependence of the population on the Bolshevik leadership.

The second group of scientific works is devoted to the Ukrainian specifics of the living and housing conditions of city dwellers, in particular in the eastern region, where industrialization processes were most active [11; 19], changes in the number and composition of residents by occupation, and the establishment of the pension system in the Ukrainian SSR [27]. A distinctive feature of the Bolshevik authorities' intervention in the processes of social development and urbanization was not only the general proletarianisation and declassification of the population, but also the disappearance of entire groups, the so-called non-working classes: the bourgeoisie, the merchant, the old intelligentsia, the wealthy peasantry, and workshop owners who employed hired labour [24, p. 69]. At the same time, scholars emphasise that in the 1920s, Bolshevik ideology was imposed on all categories of the population: from children, where a system of social education was created, based on the principle of replacing the family with an orphanage, to the political education of adults.

A separate group of studies focuses on the everyday life of Ukrainians in Poland. Ukrainian researchers refute the notion that Polish rule had positive consequences and ensured the economic and cultural development of the region. The peculiarity was that western Ukrainians found themselves within the Second Polish Republic against their will, as a result of military action, and therefore, in their eyes, the Polish state appeared as an occupying invader [26, p. 78]. The Polish regime was not democratic, but rather authoritarian with occupation-like features of governance [6], because against the backdrop of the proclaimed democratic rights and freedoms adopted by the Polish Constitution on 17 March 1921, the Polish authorities tried to destroy the very concepts of «Ukraine» and «Ukrainian», and its economic policy in the Ukrainian lands pursued the goal of slowing down development and transforming Galicia into an agrarian and raw material appendage to the indigenous Polish lands [3]. The characteristic features of the present were low wages, unfavorable sanitary and technical working conditions, non-compliance with the 8-hour working day, and rising prices for food and basic necessities, which directly affected the material situation of the population [18, p. 42].

It should be noted that the history of everyday life has deepened research interest in ordinary people, but there are insufficient comparative characteristics of the life of the Ukrainian population under the rule of the Moscow Bolsheviks and the Polish authorities.

Main Research Material

In June 1920, Poland managed to defend its independence with the help of France and repel the Bolshevik offensive, which became known as the «Miracle on the Vistula». On 12 October 1920, the leadership of Soviet Russia was forced to sign an armistice, which was followed by the Treaty of Riga on 18 March 1921. Under this treaty, Poland recognised the independence of the Ukrainian SSR and «renounced in favour of Ukraine ... all rights and claims to the lands located east» of the established border. Western Ukrainian lands, which had previously been part of the Russian Empire, also went to Poland. In turn, Soviet Russia and Ukraine renounced «all rights and claims to the lands

located west of the border» [20]. However, in August 1921, Poland openly accused the Soviet leadership of attempting to overthrow the Polish government and destroy the existing order [8, p. 5]. Poland's independence was finally secured by the decision of the Council of Ambassadors of the Entente Powers on 14 March 1923, which recognised Poland's sovereignty over Eastern Galicia and Western Volhynia.

In Ukraine, there were four Russian interventions between 1917 and 1921. However, not all of them were declared, as the aggressor often claimed that there were no Russian troops in Ukraine, but rather an «internal conflict». This refers not only to the constant violation of the treaty of 12 June 1918, according to which Russia recognised Ukraine's independence, when Lenin gave Ordzhonikidze the directive not to withdraw Russian troops, declaring them Ukrainian in order to seize resources, but also to the second Russian intervention in December 1918, when the Red Army attacked Ukraine without declaring war, and the head of the foreign policy department of Bolshevik Russia, G. Chicherin, declared that there were no Russian troops — this was a struggle between the Directory and the independent Soviet government of Ukraine. There was no adequate support for Ukraine at the international level either. Ultimately, the country was occupied.

Given the circumstances, the everyday life of the Ukrainian population in Poland and Ukraine in the 1920s developed differently. Most of Ukraine was occupied by Russian Bolsheviks, who imposed a totalitarian form of government. Poland, on the other hand, defended its independence, occupied Western Ukraine and established an authoritarian regime there. Thus, the organisation and form of government, the existing ideology, and the presence or restriction of freedom significantly influenced «people's attitudes towards everyday problems, the government, the state, and society as a whole through the prism of their personal perception of living conditions» [25, p. 7].

In Soviet Ukraine, the Bolsheviks began by plundering Ukraine and creating a «new» society, physically exterminating anyone who had a different opinion from that of the Bolshevik leaders. Communist ideology in the form of guidelines, slogans, policy documents, socio-economic models, etc. became all-encompassing. To achieve this goal, it was necessary to destroy the old structure with its economic and social ideas and spiritual traditions. New official rules and norms of behaviour were established, which often did not meet the basic needs of society, but violating them meant «resistance» to the existing regime. Of course, not all forms of behaviour that did not comply with the established norms were understood as resistance to the regime. Firstly, this applied to criminal offences, where the authorities applied a class-based approach. Secondly, phenomena that were considered «traditional» acquired a specifically Soviet context — alcoholism, religiosity, nepotism in the distribution of positions and benefits, prostitution, etc.

In the early 1920s, «socialist life» meant unemployment and the collapse of housing and communal services. Most of the remaining enterprises were small, and their total number decreased by 73%, producing

only 10% of the industrial output of 1913 [9, p. 22]. In addition, cities suffered from a permanent crisis in the transport system, drinking water supply, and a shortage of electricity and fuel. And we are not talking here about cold houses, but about the basic ability to cook food. Even in the then Soviet capital, Kharkiv, «many residents chopped up wooden beds, old chairs and tubs to cook dinner» [19, p. 46]. And what can we say about other cities in Ukraine, where the situation was much worse. The devastation even reached the toilets. For example, in many cities of Donbas, such as Yuzivka (now Donetsk), «there was not a single family that had a toilet in their apartment», and in the region as a whole, only 1.1% of the population had toilets in their homes [11, p. 89]. It should be noted that most residents generally lived in dormitories, barracks and shacks. Therefore, living in a communal apartment was considered a «blessing».

The Bolshevik leadership had no intention of meeting the needs of the people, nor did it plan to introduce standards of quality of life for city dwellers. The processes of building industrial settlements, the motives for moving the rural population to cities, and the goals of shaping the living environment were radically different from those in the West [15, p. 10]. Soviet urbanization was linked to the construction of heavy industry enterprises and the formation of the proletariat. However, by the beginning of 1920, economic ruin had led to a significant decline in the urban population. Although the new economic policy (NEP) proclaimed in March 1921 somewhat improved the situation, it did not contribute to the possibility of «proletarianising» the cities. The reaction of local communists to it was also peculiar. For example, at a party conference in Podillia, the Bolsheviks declared that «the influence of the NEP corrupts and decomposes» [24, p. 42].

The only way to resolve the demographic situation was to build large industrial facilities. Thus, in April 1923, at the 7th Conference of the Communist Party of Ukraine, it was emphasised that only «the development of industry creates an unshakable foundation for the proletarian dictatorship» [10, p. 258]. It was decided to replenish the population in cities with internal migrants and resettlers. Already in 1923, the number of urban residents increased (according to various sources, from 500,000 to 1.3 million), despite the demographic losses of almost 200,000 as a result of the famine of 1921-1923 [16, pp. 2-3; 21]. (In total, about 2 million people died of starvation in Ukraine [4, pp. 22, 25]). This increase in the urban population can be explained by the peasants who moved to the cities to escape the famine. Already in 1924, «the morning trains to Kyiv, Kharkiv, Odesa, Katerynoslav and other cities were usually overcrowded with peasants from the suburbs and villages who had already been proletarianised» [24, p. 66]. But the most effective measure was the relocation of people from relatively remote areas, mainly from Russia, to live permanently in the new territory. They lost ties with their previous place of residence and were deprived of any income other than that provided by the state at their new place of work.

The ruling idea of a «new socialist dormitory» was embodied in the construction of barracks-type dormitories and their provision to the working class as a leading social group [23, p. 25]. At the same time, a policy was pursued to improve the housing and living conditions of workers and other working people. Back in January 1921, the Council of People's Commissars issued decrees abolishing fees for workers and employees for housing, water supply, sewerage, gas, electricity, and public baths; on social security for workers, employees, and their families in case of loss of working capacity. In the spring of the same year, a resolution of the Council of People's Commissars was published on the supply of workers with shoes, clothing, soap and other consumer goods [7, p. 30]. Decrees were adopted on social insurance for workers, although this changed under the influence of the nationalisation of industry and trade during war communism, and then during the period of the New Economic Policy [2], when pensions were introduced with the aim of providing specific social assistance and promoting the advantages of Soviet power [27, p. 16]. However, social assistance was provided to urban residents. There was almost no provision for rural residents. Even urban residents were divided into four categories (special, first, second and third) in terms of the supply of food and industrial goods. At the same time, workers at state-owned enterprises received priority in social security [12, pp. 42-43]. Interestingly, the authorities also included prostitutes in the «advanced group», who also had priority in the provision of housing and work [12, p.37].

Artificial redistribution of benefits was also evident in the provision of housing in the form of various forms of «densification» of apartments. In particular, new agencies were given the right to use housing as a means of coercion to work, allowing the eviction of persons belonging to «non-working elements» without providing them with alternative accommodation [1, pp. 42-43]. This situation was enshrined in law, defining a list of citizens who were not eligible for any level of social assistance (persons who used hired labour, lived on non-labour income, private traders, monks and clergy, former gendarmes, the insane, and those convicted of mercenary and shameful crimes). At the same time, the main sign of «social inferiority» was past social status.

The struggle against the nobility, landowners and bourgeoisie, and later against skilled workers and peasants, the introduction of «the class dictatorship of the proletariat as a necessary transitional stage towards the destruction of class distinctions in general» [14, p. 91] with the aim of forming a new type of person – a «builder of communism» – manifested itself in the reality of that time – militant atheism, Russification, and cultural deprivation. This is not surprising, since the lumpenised strata of society simply did not have basic rules and norms of behavior, moral values, or even hygiene. Thus, in the reports of the municipal services departments, we find conclusions that «the unsanitary habits of city dwellers cannot be overcome in the absence of toilets» [11, p. 89]. At the same time, in large industrial cities, the transformation of morals and the devaluation of values took place more rapidly [5, p.

381]. In such cities, especially in those regions of Ukraine where large industrial facilities were being built and the population was being «proletarianised», there was simply no urban culture. Ninety percent of such cities were built up with barracks (designed for 80-120 people each), «there was mud up to the knees and wooden boardwalks, which during the spring and autumn rains were thrown from above directly onto the soggy clay so that pedestrians could at least somehow make their way and not sink into the dough-like mess» [15, p. 12].

At the same time, all the anomalies of Soviet urban society: alcoholism, crime, prostitution, etc. were considered remnants of capitalism. In party and state documents of the early 1920s, the term «social diseases» even appeared. The Soviet specificity was also expressed in a special system of the authorities' attitude towards alcoholics, criminals, prostitutes, and suicides. And «godless life», communal living, restrictions on the rights of former apartment owners, and denunciations were quite normal phenomena for Soviet society at that time [13, p. 36]. At the same time, the authorities constantly instilled in workers the idea of their vanguard role, and on this basis, the so-called proletarian arrogance developed in them — a feeling of permissiveness and impunity, which led to numerous cases of hooliganism, when workers beat up specialists, engineers and directors without any reason [17].

The situation was somewhat different for the population of western Ukrainian cities under Polish rule. Under the 1921 Treaty of Riga, Ukrainians were granted «on the basis of equality of nationalities, all rights ensuring the free development of culture, language and religious practices». They could develop their language, organise educational institutions and develop their national culture [20]. In 1923, in Paris, the Council of Ambassadors of the Entente proposed that the Polish government grant Galicia self-government. However, the previously agreed granting of political autonomy to the region and the holding of a referendum by the Polish side was rejected because the Galician Regional Sejm and the Regional Council had been abolished in 1918, and in 1919, Ukrainians were banned from studying at universities in Lviv unless they had served in the Polish army and taken Polish citizenship. In 1920, an illegitimate census of the population of Western Ukraine was conducted for conscription into the Polish Army, and in the same year, the use of the names «Western Ukraine» and «Ukrainian» was banned in official documents, and instead, the terms «Małopolska Wschodnia» or «Eastern Małopolska» and «Rusyn» were introduced. Those Ukrainians who refused to register as Poles were dismissed from government positions. For example, in 1920 alone, 5,000 railway workers of non-Polish nationality were dismissed. All this took place against the backdrop of proclaimed democratic rights and freedoms, including self-government, adopted by the Polish Constitution on 17 March 1921. However, in Western Ukraine (Lviv, Ternopil and Stanislav provinces), self-government was left to the Austro-Hungarian system adopted in 1886.

In 1923, a policy of forced assimilation of national minorities (incorporation) and the creation of a single-nation state began. At that time, the country's policy was effectively determined by the People's Union, which did not recognise Ukrainians (as well as Belarusians and Lithuanians) as a separate nation, but only as an ethnographic group of the single Polish nation. At the same time, it had a pro-Russian orientation, as the Second Polish Republic was to be revived in its former territories, dividing Ukraine with the Russian Empire (albeit already Bolshevik). In 1924 the «Grabski Law» abolished Ukrainian schools and replaced them with «utrakvistychny» (bilingual) schools, in which subjects were gradually taught in Polish. The use of the Ukrainian language was also banned in all state institutions, without exception, including local government. European countries played an important role in this, investing funds in the Polish economy and demanding the establishment of «strong government». Indeed, the country soon stabilized its currency and began to emerge from the economic crisis.

The regime was enforced by an extensive system of state police, which, in addition to law enforcement activities, also performed functions of political pressure: it investigated political cases, prepared reports on the mood of the Ukrainian population, assessed political and public organizations, and monitored Ukrainian civil servants. In 1921, the position of «confidant» was introduced in its staff – a secret agent whose task was to provide information about anti-state activities [6].

After the coup d'état of 1926, the situation changed somewhat. Józef Piłsudski's policy of «Prometheism» consisted in restoring the state «from sea to sea» while helping to liberate Ukrainians from Moscow's rule by uniting them with Poland on a federal basis. To implement this policy, a special department of nationalities was created in 1926, which sought not to «rewrite» nationality, but to make Ukrainians patriots of the Second Polish Republic. However, in the 1930s, a «pacification» campaign was launched with the aim of forcibly assimilating and destroying the Ukrainian resistance movement. In 1934, the Bereza Kartuska concentration camp was established for Ukrainians who fought for their rights. Under the pretext of fighting terrorism, searches were conducted, libraries were burned, schools were closed, and associations were banned.

Everyday life in western Ukrainian cities also differed significantly from life in the Ukrainian SSR. There was no red terror, famines, large-scale repression and intimidation of the population, nor was there a policy of forced industrialisation with labour quotas and a card system or the formation of a proletariat. Polish legislation regulated the conclusion of contracts between employers and employees, according to which the worker undertook to comply with internal regulations and perform certain work, and the employer undertook to pay wages and provide appropriate working conditions [18, p. 35]. At the same time, the territory was divided into two parts. Territory «B» – Ukrainian, was deliberately transformed into a raw material appendage. The industry was dominated by oil production, wood processing and mineral processing. Almost no investments were made here, and the issuance of permits

to open new enterprises was hampered in every way. However, at the end of the 1920s, Ukrainian entrepreneurs received financial support aimed at developing cooperative associations, but high railway tariffs reduced the competitiveness of Ukrainian-made goods compared to products from territory «A» – Poland.

The Polish state was, on the one hand, an authoritarian state, and on the other, a parliamentary and pluralistic one, which gave Ukrainians a legitimate way to fight for their rights and, albeit in limited forms, to develop their culture, national identity, collective and religious life [26, p. 82]. However, the low standard of living in Western Ukraine caused a wave of labour emigration. Between 1920 and 1939, approximately 100,000 Ukrainian migrants arrived in the United States, 70,000 in Canada, almost 10,000 in Brazil, and over 40,000 in Argentina. Ukrainians also migrated to other Latin American countries, such as Uruguay and Paraguay. The total number of emigrants from Western Ukraine exceeded 220,000 [3].

Conclusions

Thus, the armed seizure of Ukraine led to the establishment of a totalitarian form of government by the Russian occupying authorities. Ukrainians experienced terror, repression, organised famine and genocide. Fear and defencelessness towards the authorities reigned in the country. The Bolsheviks physically exterminated all dissidents and instilled hatred towards them. People had to be loyal to the party and the regime to the point of self-sacrifice, work, live in barracks, be satisfied with the minimum living and other conditions that were barely sufficient for physical survival, and carry out any tasks assigned by the party. The population of Western Ukraine in the Polish state also suffered from various political restrictions and a low standard of living compared to Poles. However, they were not restricted in their right to move freely, there was no nationalisation of property or mass looting, no monopolisation of power with the violent imposition of the Bolshevik worldview and the complete physical destruction of certain social groups, as well as anyone else who had an opinion different from that of the Bolshevik leaders.

Experience with Russia also shows that it perceives any signed peace treaty as preparation for an armed attack, and once it has seized territory, it plunders and commits genocide. After all, not only Ukrainians who were occupied in the 1920s were subjected to repression, but also the population occupied in the 1930s, when Hitler and Stalin divided Poland (Molotov-Ribbentrop Pact). From September 1939 to June 1941, repression affected 10% of the population. Around 500,000 Polish citizens were arrested and imprisoned, not to mention those who were deported.

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